

EFFECT OF COVID-19 TO TRACKING THE POVERTY ERADICATION OF SDGs IN ODISHA

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has created previously unheard-of difficulties for the entire world, affecting social progress and economic stability among other aspects of life. The purpose of this paper is to provide insights into how the pandemic has affected Odisha's efforts to eradicate poverty as they relate to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework. The main aim of the study is to examine the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) target-wise budget allocation Across the Goal. 1 to eradicate extreme poverty in 2030. This study examines at the relationship between COVID-19 and the progress made in reaching SDG targets related to eradicating poverty, with an emphasis on Odisha, a state with high rates of poverty and continuing SDGs initiatives. The present study found that the Goal 4 on Quality education has the highest allocation share and constitutes 14.35% of the total budget followed by Goal 10 on reducing inequalities. Transfers from the State also have a significant contribution of 13.26% for the achievement of the goal objectives. It aims to identify potential strategies and interventions to mitigate the adverse effects of the pandemic on poverty eradication efforts, thereby contributing to the resilience and adaptability of development initiatives in Odisha.

Keywords: Covid-19, Poverty Eradication, SDGs, Odisha, Socio-Economic Indicators

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Introduction:

The relationship between public health emergencies and socioeconomic inequalities has come into sharper focus since the COVID-19 pandemic, especially with regard to India's efforts to meet the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets. The COVID-19 pandemic has made poverty problems worse, making it more difficult to achieve the SDGs' goal of eradicating poverty (Pradhan et al. 2023). This paper provides foundations for an investigation into the complex interplay among the pandemic's effects, efforts to reduce poverty, and India's advancement toward the SDG targets. We can gain a better understanding of the challenges associated with eradicating poverty in the face of a global health crisis by looking at these links.

Globally, the COVID-19 epidemic has affected many aspects of life, including socioeconomic development initiatives. Poverty eradication is a top priority in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are designed to empower marginalized communities and promote inclusive growth. The pandemic has made it difficult to monitor and maintain the progress made in the Indian state of Odisha, where efforts have been undertaken to reduce poverty (Gupta et al., 2021). This study delves into the intricate interplay between the COVID-19 crisis and the pursuit of SDG-driven poverty eradication in Odisha. Understanding this nexus is crucial for policymakers, development practitioners, and communities to formulate effective responses and strategies for resilience and recovery.

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted various socio-economic activities, exacerbating existing vulnerabilities and inequalities in Odisha. Lockdown measures, restrictions on mobility, and disruptions in supply chains have severely impacted livelihoods, particularly those of marginalized and economically disadvantaged groups (Gupta et al., 2021). The sudden loss of income, coupled with limited access to essential services and resources, has pushed many households into poverty or further entrenched their precarious financial situations. The epidemic has caused pressure on the healthcare system and taken funds and attention away from current development priorities, which could impede the achievement of SDG targets (Pradhan et al. 2023). Since the focus of efforts has shifted to stopping the virus's transmission and reducing its socioeconomic effects, it is critical to evaluate how the pandemic may affect Odisha's attempts to eradicate poverty differently (Gupta et al., 2021). This study aims to shed light on the complex dynamics at play through rigorous analysis and

empirical evidence. It will also offer insights into the opportunities, challenges, and potential pathways for mitigating the negative effects of COVID-19 on the tracking of poverty eradication under the SDGs in Odisha.

Review of Literature:

Pradhan et al. (2023), in their paper analyse the ability to assess the state of Odisha's chances and obstacles for reaching the SDGs in the future, as well as the support that policy already provides or needs in this regard. In order to accomplish this goal, the relationship between public social sector spending and the Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) was examined using econometric analysis. This allowed for the assessment of the necessary investments to be made in order to realize the SDGs. According to the study's findings, increasing public spending on the social sector can statistically significantly lower the MPI, which may make it easier for the state to meet the SDGs. The authors propose that, given the current environment, greater emphasis should be placed on improved governance and more effective policy and program execution.

Gupta et al. (2021), have analyse the policies of the international community and individual states reveal a lack of empathy for underdeveloped countries and their citizens. This study discusses the development issues brought to light by the COVID-19 pandemic and the lessons that can be used to the design of recovery strategies. According to the study's findings, underlying "drivers" and "pressures" were disregarded in favour of a speedy economic recovery. Additionally, they have discovered that going back to business as usual with government funding will result in a vicious loop that exacerbates the factors contributing to the pandemic, including socioeconomic inequality, ecological degradation, and domestic abuse. The present study concludes that the lost years for development did not commence in 2020 with the onset of COVID-19; the downward trend has actually been waxing over the past three decades.

Fagbemi (2021), have examined the COVID-19's spill over effect on Nigeria's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as shown by the methodical depiction of the most frequent occurrences. The study found that many other important socioeconomic concerns (such as employment, infrastructure development, and education) suffered from neglect or were ignored as a result of the focus on the COVID-19 cases. Nigeria's development potential is thus threatened by the current crisis, since recovery may take longer than expected, particularly in the post-COVID-19 environment. Therefore, it is imperative to acknowledge

the need of establishing a robust institutional regulatory framework and the necessary resources, both material and financial, to enable long-term economic transformation.

Alkiren et al. (2021), in their article examined that progress is being challenged by the COVID-19 epidemic and its accompanying economic downturn, which is having a severe influence on several dimensions of poverty. This study provides micro-simulations of possible short-term pandemic repercussions under alternate scenarios by utilizing recent assessments of food insecurity and school closures conducted by UN agencies. The 2020 update of the global MPI is based on nationally representative datasets, which are used in these simulations. According to the 2020 Global MPI, the results across 70 countries, which make up 89% of the world's impoverished, show that the different scenarios might potentially set back multidimensional poverty reduction by 3.6-20.9 years. The authors are argued that the extent to which such disruptions result in persistent increases of poverty and deprivations may be attenuated by appropriate policy responses.

Barfi & Vitenu-Sackey (2021), have seeks to evaluate the pandemic's effects on reducing poverty and the world GDP by taking into account the varied effects of each country in a panel analysis. Robust least square regression techniques and other econometric panel approaches are used in this work. The study's conclusions state that the spread of the illness and the stringency of many people have had a negative impact on economic growth and the reduction of poverty. The report suggests that governments make investments in the development of health and education systems as well as boost their economies to generate jobs that might spur economic growth and reduce poverty.

Objectives:

(1) To examine the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) target-wise budget allocation Across the Goal. 1 by 2030, to eradicate extreme poverty.

Data Sources and Methodology:

The present study is based on secondary data to examine the eradicate poverty in Odisha. The study is basically in descriptive nature. The study has based on secondary data from the official website of SDG Budget 2022-23, Government of Odisha. In this study analyse the demand for grand of Odisha's Budget allocation and expenditure details in SDGs Goal 1.

Result and Discussion:

Effective resource allocation is essential to attaining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030, especially in areas facing persistent issues like extreme poverty. This study examines the target-wise budget allocation across SDG Goal 1 eradicating extreme poverty

with a focus on Odisha, India. Through an analysis of resource allocation strategies, this study seeks to determine how financial priorities and developmental goals line up. By means of thorough analysis, it endeavours to uncover prospects for optimizing budgetary allotments in order to efficiently tackle poverty and promote sustainable development in Odisha, thus making a contribution to the wider global objective of SDG achievement.

Table No. 1- SDG Budget Across Goals (Expenditure in Crore):

	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23
Goal 1 (Poverty eradication)	10185.1	10583.5	13634.2
Total	114580.7	143172.3	184844.4
Percentage of Goal 1 to Total Expenditure	8.88	7.39	7.37

Sources: SDG Budget 2022-23, Government of Odisha

The Table No. 1 shows that the percentage of Goal 1 to total expenditure. According to the data we can see that gradually the expenditure on goal 1 decreased from 2020 to 2023 but this is not a good sign for the state. Because we know that Odisha is a state having more poor people so we have to increase our percentage of share in the poverty reduction programme. But due to a shortage of budget govt. reduced the expenditure on it. SDGs Budget can provide useful insights into the public finance strategy of Odisha from a SDGs perspective, the process and methodology adopted for the purpose have significant potential for further deepening and greater granularity. The mapping and assignment of weights has an unavoidable space for subjectivity, although it has been sought to be optimally narrowed. This being said, the entire exercise has been done with as much objectivity as possible and the SDG Budget positively plays a key role in driving the SDG Agenda in Odisha’s development.

Fig No.1- Department-wise SDG BudgetShare-2022-23:

This section demonstrates the total outlay of the SDG budget based on different variables and across different departments. The department expenditure from all the schemes and programmes, mapped to the goals, has been analyzed from the lens of its share as part of the total expenditure of the state of Odisha for the fiscal year 2022-23 BE, across the type and kind of expenditure.

Figure no. 1 shows that the proportion of each SDG to the total budget outlay. The analysis reflects that Goal 4 on Quality education has the highest allocation share and constitutes 14.35% of the total budget followed by Goal 10 on reducing inequalities. Goal 1 for Poverty Reduction, which budget share is less than the other six budget shares. So, to reduce quality and poverty the Odisha govt. has to spend on more poverty eradication programs and also more focus on goal no.1. Because according to the report of Indian Expresses News, Odisha is having highest number of unemployed youths all over India. Which adversely affects poverty as well as the reason of having a poorer state, Goal 1 (dedicated to ending poverty everywhere) has 7.37% share in 2022-23 BE in the total SDG budget outlay with a total of Rs. 13634.19 crore dedicated to achieving this goal. The target-wise total allocation made for different Departments is reflected in the following table.2.

Table no. 2- Target-wise Allocations (in crores):

2020-21 BE	2021-22	2022-23 RE	
1.1 By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day	0.68	3.17	2.50
1.3 Implement nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including floors, and by 2030 achieve substantial coverage of the poor and the vulnerable	3638.63	3778.75	4308.46
1.4 By 2030, ensure that all men and women, in particular the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, ownership and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology and financial services, including microfinance	5081.42	4483.14	6480.94

1.5 By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters	37.12	36.46	33.67
1.a Ensure significant mobilization of resources from a variety of sources, including through enhanced development cooperation, to provide adequate and predictable means for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, to implement programmes and policies to end poverty in all its dimensions	1427.23	2281.99	2808.61
Total	10185.06	10583.51	13634.19

Sources: SDG Budget 2022-23, Government of Odisha

The table no. 2 shows that Target-wise Allocations in Odisha. Among all departments, the Panchayati Raj & Drinking Water Department had the highest share for this goal in 2022-23 BE with 72.05% of the total allocation for the goal fall in gender it, followed by the Department of Social Security & Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities that supports 12.79% allocation contributing towards this goal. The contribution of the Health & Family Welfare Department and Mission Shakti Department is 5.86% and 3.53%, respectively. The contribution of different Departments to Goal-1 in descending order is depicted in figure-1.

Figure.1. Department Expenditure Share -2022-23 (BE)

Furthermore, a detailed breakdown of the expenditure contributing towards the goal

shows that 26.80% of the budget allocation being utilized for the achievement of this goal comes from the state sector schemes, amounting to about Rs. 3654.55crore, whereas 0.42% of it comes from the Establishment, Operations and Maintenance costs of the relevant departments with an expenditure of approximately Rs. 57.76 crore. Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) split a large percentage of the goal contribution (59.12%) between the state and the center, with the proportions varying based on the individual schemes and programs. Additionally, transfers from the State contribute significantly—13.26%—to the accomplishment of the aim objectives. Furthermore, the Disaster Response Funds are being used for about Rs. 53.67 crore, or nearly 0.39% of the budgetary amount. The expenditure on the goal from different sources is given in table-3.

Table no. 3 – Expenditure on Goal-1 across Allocation Source (In crore):

	2020-21	2021-22RE	2022-23BE
EOM Expenditure	44.26	43.44	57.76
State Sector Schemes(SSS)	1008.06	1970.96	3654.55
Centrally Sponsored Schemes(CSS)	6541.60	6751.14	8060.09
Transfers from State(TFS)	2556.03	1781.51	1808.12
Disaster Response Funds	35.12	36.46	53.67
Total	10185.06	10583.51	13634.19

Sources: SDG Budget 2022-23, Government of Odisha

The table no. 3 analyzed a detailed breakdown of the expenditure contributing towards the goal shows that 26.80% of the budget allocation being utilized for the achievement of this goal comes from the state sector schemes, amounting to about Rs. 3654.55crore, whereas 0.42% of it comes from the Establishment, Operations and Maintenance costs of the relevant departments with an expenditure of approximately Rs. 57.76 crore. Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS) split a large percentage of the goal contribution (59.12%) between the state and the center, with the proportions varying based on the individual schemes and programs. Additionally, transfers from the State contribute significantly—13.26%—to the accomplishment of the aim objectives. Furthermore, the Disaster Response Funds are being used for about Rs. 53.67 crore, or nearly 0.39% of the budgetary amount. The expenditure on the goal from different sources is given in Table No. 3.

Table No. 4- Different Types of Poverty Eradication Programmes Are Implemented By The Govt. By 2030: (Value in Lakhs)

Targets	S l.	SchemeName	2020-21	2021-22 RE	2022-23 BE	Dept.Name	Sche me- types
Goal-1:End Poverty in a lilt forms everywhere							
1.1 : By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25aday	1	2429 - Poverty and Human Development Monitoring Agency(PHDMA)	67.50	317.00	250.00	P&C	SSS
		Total	67.50	317.00	250.00		
1.3 : Implement nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including floors, and by 2030 achieve substantial coverage	1	0864 - Maintenance of water supply & sanitary installation under Chief Engineer, Rural Works	405.54	460.00	504.45	RD	EOM
	2	0959-National Old age Pension to destitute	35546.82	61879.87	64832.01	SS&EPD	CSS
	3	1872-National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme	64005.72	84620.14	79600.00	PR&DW	CSS
	4	2097-Madhubabu Pension for Destitute	42256.73	68580.36	72917.65	SS&EPD	SSS
	5	2161-Rural Infrastructure Development Fund(RIDF)	0.00	0.99	4700.00	WR	SSS
	6	2245-NREGS Head Quarter Cell	58.90	89.03	239.48	PR&DW	CSS
	7	2255-Multi-sector Development Programme	0.00	382.25	0.00	ST&SC Dev.	CSS
	8	2432-Indira Gandhi National Disable Pension Scheme	2409.99	4895.83	5080.69	SS&EPD	CSS
	9	2433-Indira Gandhi National Widow Pension Scheme	17744.54	24881.84	30483.90	SS&EPD	CSS

of the poor and the vulnerable	10	2678-Conditional cash transfer for Pregnant women(MAMATA)	11361.48	13945.63	12370.09	W& CD	SSS
	11	2792-Ex-gratia & Compensation	0.00	0.00	2000.01	D& M	DRF
	12	2916-National Urban Livelihood Mission	0.00	0.00	419.20	MissionS hakti	CSS
	13	2948 - Management Support to Rural Development Programmes and Strengthening District Planning Process etc.	133.87	185.03	340.38	PR&DW	CSS
	14	2950-National Rural Livelihood Mission(NRLM)	32084.73	50626.61	36187.72	PR&DW	CSS
	15	2991-PradhanMantriAdarshaGramYojana(PMAGY)	0.00	2000.02	26948.80	ST&SC Dev.	CSS
	16	3013 - National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) Head Quarters Cell	248.17	450.02	894.40	PR&DW	CSS

Targets	Sl.	SchemeName	2020-21	2021-22 RE	2022-23 BE	Dept.Nam e	Scheme -types
	17	3084 - Operationalisation of Urban Hostel Complexes(A KANKSHYA)	938.22	318.47	342.53	ST&SC Dev.	SSS
	18	3240-Maternity Benefit Programme-MAMATA	0.00	0.01	0.00	W& CD	CSS
	19	3258-National Family Benefit Scheme	912.60	1181.72	1200.00	SS&EPD	CSS
	20	3340-Pradhan Mantri MatruVandanaYojana	0.00	0.02	0.02	W& CD	CSS
	21	3383-Pradhan Mantri Jan Vikash Karyakarm	250.00	1800.00	0.00	ST&SC Dev.	CSS
	22	3384-Biju Swasthya Kalyana Yojana	42302.10	54548.75	79931.55	H& FW	SSS
	23	3425 - Basic Grant to Rural Local Bodies as	112900.00	0.00	0.00	PR&DW	TFS

		recommended by 15 th Finance Commission					
	24	3451-Mission Shakti Programme	303.50	4528.50	6737.10	W& CD	SSS
	25	3502-Implementation of SCA to TSS	0.00	2500.00	0.00	ST&SC Dev.	CSS
	26	3518-SAMARTHYA	0.00	0.01	0.00	W& CD	CSS
	27	3528-National Rural Economic Transformation Project(NRETP)	0.00	0.00	4364.24	Missi on Shakti	CSS
	28	3529-Start-up Village Entrepreneurship Programme(SVEP)	0.00	0.00	480.02	Missi on Shakti	CSS
	29	3603-Social Security Insurance	0.00	0.00	272.07	W& CD	CSS
		Total	363862.89	377875.08	430846.29		
1.4 : By 2030, ensure that all men and women, in particular the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, ownership and control over land and other	1	0164-Compensation and Assignments	10.17	20.58	852.79	Revenue	SSS
	2	0569-Grants and Assistance	2951.00	3540.00	4920.15	Forest &Env.	EOM
	3	1004 - Odisha Forest Sector Development Project (EAP,JBIC(Japan)assisted)	44.48	0.00	0.00	Forest &Env.	SSS
	4	1448-Tahasil Establishment	2000.00	1336.82	2033.62	Revenue	SSS
	5	2055-Biju Grama Jyoti	497.62	2700.00	3750.00	Energy	SSS
	6	2357-Grants to Lord Sri	10.00	3.00	10.00	Law	SSS

forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology and financial services, including microfinance	7	Jagannath Temple 2429 - Poverty and Human Development Monitoring Agency(PHDMA)	67.50	317.00	250.00	P&C	SSS
	8	2468-Biju Saharanchal Vidyutikaran Yojana	0.00	150.00	90.00	Energy	SSS
	9	2474-Conferment of Land Rights	0.00	0.01	0.01	Revenue	SSS

Targets	Sl.	SchemeName	2020-21	2021-22 RE	2022-23 BE	Dept.Nam e	Scheme-types
	10	2916-National Urban Livelihood Mission	1338.31	1633.09	4082.57	Missio nShakt i	CSS
	11	3014-Biju Pucca Ghar	0.00	0.00	4000.00	PR&DW	SSS
	12	3075-ABBAAS-Odisha Urban Housing Mission(OUHM)	82.50	49.99	25.00	H&UD	SSS
	13	3122-Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana(Rural)- Biju Pucca Ghar	493312.27	426400.00	550584.00	PR&DW	CSS
	14	3127- SyamaPrasadaMukharje eRURBANMission	540.00	2400.00	0.00	PR&DW	CSS
	15	3274-Pradhan Mantri Awaas Yojana(Urban)	5573.65	9173.38	0.00	H&UD	CSS
	16	3304-Sahaj Bijli Har Ghar Yojona(Rural)-	488.80	100.00	1000.00	Energy	SSS

		Saubhagya					
	17	3328-Relocation of villages from Reserve forest and sanctuaries.	156.00	156.00	156.00	Forest & Env.	SSS
	18	3359-Jaga Mission	0.00	0.03	1000.00	H&UD	SSS
	19	3421-PCCF Kendu Leaf	1069.26	333.75	340.22	Forest & Env.	EOM
	20	N17-0002-State Support to MGNREGS	0.00	0.00	3000.00	PR&DW	SSS
		Total	508141.56	448313.65	648094.36		
1.5 : By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate - related extreme events and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters	1	1021-Other Relief Measures	200.00	0.00	0.00	D& M	SSS
	2	1183 - Relief Expenditure met from National Disaster Response Fund(NDRF)	5.64	78.39	0.03	D& M	DRF
	3	1192-Repair Renovation and Restoration	1080.09	480.00	480.00	D& M	DRF
	4	2792-Ex-gratia & Compensation	2192.29	2342.00	2362.00	D& M	DRF
	5	2796-Assistance to Farmers/Fishermen/Artisans etc	233.73	745.81	525.00	D& M	DRF
		Total	3711.75	3646.20	3367.03		
1.a : Ensure significant	1	0922-Miscellaneous	0.00	9.80	10.80	F&ARD	EOM
	2	1168-Recruitment and	19.45	20.00	32.00	Revenue	SSS

mobilization of resources from a variety of sources, including through enhanced development cooperation, in order to provide adequate and predictable means for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, to implement programmes and policies to end poverty in all its dimensions		Departmental Examination					
	3	1448-Tahasil Establishment	0.00	3.20	6.40	Revenue	SSS
	4	2255-Multi-sector Development Programme	0.00	15.00	0.00	ST&SC Dev.	CSS
	5	3227-Revolving Fund for MGNREGS wages	0.00	50000.00	100000.00	PR&DW	SSS
	6	3462-Devolution of Funds to PRIs under the award of 5th SFC	45463.60	46045.41	45754.50	PR&DW	TFS
	7	3463-Grants and Assistance under the award of 5th SFC	40789.50	42389.50	42391.00	PR&DW	TFS

Targets	Sl.	SchemeName	2020-21	2021-22 RE	2022-23 BE	Dept. Name	Scheme types
	8	3469 - Tied Grants to local bodies recommended by the 15th Finance Commission	56450.00	50070.00	51840.00	PR&DW	TFS
	9	3492-15 th FC Grants:	0.00	33380	34560.	PR&DW	TFS

		Untied Grant to Rural Local Bodies		.00	00		
	10	3493-15 th FC Grants: Conversion of Rural PHC & CSs into Health and wellness centre	0.00	6266. 49	6266.5 0	PR&DW	TFS
		Total	142722.55	22819 9.40	280861 .20		
		Goal-1:GrandTotal	1018506.	10583	136341		
			2	51.3	8.8		
			5	3	8		

Sources: SDG Budget 2022-23, Government of Odisha

The table no. 4 shows the different types of poverty eradication programmes that are implemented by the govt. by 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day and which programmes come under which dept, that are mentioned. Given these developments, the Odisha government has directed more of its attention into making sure that the SDGs are successfully incorporated into the state's planning and budgetary procedures. The state's Planning and Convergence Department and Finance Department have worked extremely hard to fortify the connections to SDG-aligned indicators and financing strategies with an emphasis on SDG-based governance since releasing the first-ever SDG Budget Statement in tandem with the 2021–22 state budget. Going one step further, the Finance Department, in coordination with other key departments, has led public finance innovations having strong linkages with SDG-based budgeting such as the Public Expenditure reviews in areas like children's development, climate change, gender, nutrition, social justice and poverty reduction.

Conclusion and Suggestions:

The COVID-19 pandemic has presented unprecedented challenges to Odisha's progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in eradicating poverty. The crisis has exacerbated existing vulnerabilities and deepened socio-economic disparities across the state. It has, however, also highlighted how crucial it is to implement focused interventions and resilient methods in order to lessen the impact that these crises have on the most vulnerable groups. It is crucial to monitor the interplay between COVID-19

response measures and attempts to eradicate poverty in order to inform future policies and initiatives. Odisha can use the lessons learnt from the epidemic to prioritize inclusive and equitable measures and use them to accelerate progress towards attaining the SDGs. To address the underlying causes of poverty and promote resilience and sustainable development in all spheres of society, government agencies, civil society organizations, and the corporate sector must work together. The results of the study reflect that the expenditure on goal 1 decreased from 2020 to 2023 but this is not a good sign for the state. The analysis shows that Goal 4 on Quality education has the highest allocation share and constitutes 14.35% of the total budget followed by Goal 10 on reducing inequalities. Among all departments, the Panchayati Raj & Drinking Water Department had the highest share for this goal in 2022-23 BE with 72.05% of the total allocation for the goal fall in gender it, followed by the Department of Social Security & Empowerment of Persons with Disabilities that supports 12.79% allocation contributing towards this goal. The present study also shows that Transfers from the State also have a significant contribution of 13.26% for the achievement of the goal objectives. Further, almost 0.39% of the budget allocation of approximately Rs.53.67 crore is being utilized for the Disaster Response Funds. A significant portion of the goal contribution (59.12%) is shared by the centre and state under Centrally Sponsored Schemes (CSS), with varying proportions between the Centre and the State, depending upon the respective schemes and programmes. by 2030, eradicate extreme poverty for all people everywhere, currently measured as people living on less than \$1.25 a day and which programmes come under which dept, that are mentioned.

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on poverty eradication efforts in Odisha, the present study recognize the critical need for comprehensive tracking mechanisms aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To maintain resilience and progress towards the SDGs, the present study policy intends to connect initiatives for eradicating poverty with COVID-19 reaction measures. Perform frequent vulnerability assessments to determine whether people are more vulnerable to poverty as a result of COVID-19. The most afflicted areas should receive resources and initiatives first, therefore use demographic analysis and geographic mapping. Establish a framework for policy that is adaptable to changing COVID-19 dynamics and socioeconomic issues. Always assess the success of initiatives and modify plans in response to feedback and real-time data.

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